

Chemical Constituents of the Leaves of *Marsilea minuta* Linn

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An unsymmetrical hydroxyketone, 3-hydroxytriacontan-11-one has been obtained from the petroleum ether extract of the leaves of *Marsilea minuta* Linn. This is the first report in plant of a C₃₀ ketone with a hydroxyl group. In addition to this a mixture of secondary alcohols with carbon content from C₂₇-C₃₁ has also been found. Alcohols with odd number of carbon atoms are dominant. One of the major components is identical with hentriacontan-16-ol which is prepared synthetically by the borohydride reduction of palmitone. A mixture of normal hydrocarbons with C₂₇, C₂₉, C₃₁ and C₃₃ predominating has also been obtained from this fraction. Methylamine, β -sitosterol and a waxy material which contain a mixture of hydrocarbons and high molecular weight esters have been obtained from the chloroform extract. The claim of Chatterjee *et al.* that marsiline, a ketonic compound, m.p. 85°-86° was isolated from this fraction cannot however be substantiated. The alcoholic extract of the leaves contains a saponin which on acid hydrolysis affords a sapogenin m.p. 304°-305°.

MARSILEA minuta Linn¹⁻³ (Marsileaceae) is a common fern, popular drug in folk medicine. Leaves and whole plants are used for sedation and in insomnia. Many of the Indian floras refer this common Indian species to *Marsilea quadrifolia* Linn⁴. The only compound isolated so far from this plant is a ketone m.p. 85-86° by Chatterjee *et al.*⁵ Our interest for the reinvestigation of the plant was revived while searching for saponin bearing plant as an aqueous solution of the leaves gives a stable froth indicating the presence of saponin in it. As such a detailed chemical examination was undertaken.

The air dried powdered leaves were extracted successively with petroleum ether (60°-80°), chloroform and ethanol in a soxhlet. The residue from petroleum ether extract was subjected to chromatographic separation over Brockmann alumina (Table I). The solvents were petroleum ether, (40°-60°), benzene, ether and methanol used successively in a gradient elution procedure, when 3 major components were obtained. Their purity was assayed by T. L. C. It is worthwhile mentioning that while working with the higher aliphatic hydrocarbon, ketone and alcohol the T. L. C. often fails to give true picture. There are some inseparable mixtures which can only be detected by G. L. C.

Treatment of the fractions of Table I

Each fraction from A₁-A₂₀ was examined separately by T. L. C. when a single strip was obtained. These fractions showed no absorption at 1720-1740

cm⁻¹ or 3600-3400 cm⁻¹ in the I.R. confirming the absence of carbonyl and hydroxy containing compounds. G.L.C. indicated a mixture of normal hydrocarbons with C₂₇, C₂₉, C₃₁ and C₃₃ predominating.

Fraction A₂₁-A₄₅ gave only a very small quantity of material and was found to be mixtures by T.L.C.

Fraction A₄₆-A₁₁₀ eluted with petroleum ether (40°-60°) and benzene gave one elongated distinct strip in T.L.C. G.L.C. revealed that it is a mixture of several components. These fractions were mixed together and chromatographed over Argentized silica-gel (Table II).

Treatment of the fraction of Table II

Fraction B₁₁-B₂₀ eluted with petroleum ether (40°-60°) and benzene gave a solid m.p. 93°. No peak for =C=O or -OH was found in the I.R. and it was found to be a mixture of hydrocarbon by G.L.C.

Fractions B₂₁-B₈₀ eluted with petroleum ether (40°-60°) and benzene gave a solid m.p. 95°C. I.R. absorption at 3600-3400 cm⁻¹ shows the presence of hydroxyl containing compounds and G.L.C. revealed that it is a mixture. It was then rechromatographed over Argentized silica gel (Table III).

Fractions B₈₆-B₁₀₅ eluted with benzene and petroleum ether (40°-60°) was found to be a single component by T.L.C. and G.L.C. (Fig. 1 and 2). The residue

TABLE I

Fractions*	Eluents	Nature of the product	Remarks
A ₁ -A ₂₀	Petroleum Ether (40-60)	White solid m.p. 80-81°C 105 mg.	Mixture of Hydrocarbons by I. R. & G. L. C. report.
A ₂₁ -A ₄₅	-do-	White solid m.p. 88°C. 15 mg.	Mixture
A ₄₆ -A ₈₀	Petroleum Ether : Benzene (3:1)	White solid m.p. 91°C. 150 mg.	Mixture by T. L. C. and G. L. C. report.
A ₈₁ -A ₁₁₀	Petroleum Ether : Benzene (1:1)	White solid m.p. 91°C. 105 mg.	-do-
A ₁₁₁ -A ₁₃₀	Benzene	Nil	
A ₁₃₁ -A ₁₄₀	Benzene : Ether (3:1)	Little yellow solid 8 mg. m.p. 73°C.	
A ₁₄₁ -A ₁₄₇	Benzene : Ether (1:1)	Very little yellow solid. 5 mg. m.p. 75°C.	
A ₁₄₈ -A ₁₅₀	Ether	Nil	
A ₁₅₁ -A ₁₅₃	Ether : Methanol	Little oily liquid 12 mg.	
A ₁₅₄ -A ₁₅₆	Methanol	-do- 8 mg.	

* Each fraction contains 10 ml. of eluent.

TABLE II

Fractions*	Eluents	Nature of the product.	Remarks
B ₁ -B ₁₀	Petroleum Ether (40-60)	Nil	
B ₁₁ -B ₂₀	Petroleum Ether : Benzene (3:1)	White solid m.p. 93°C. 40 mg.	Mixture of hydrocarbon by I. R. and G. L. C. report.
B ₂₁ -B ₈₀	-do-	White solid. m.p. 95°C. 120 mg.	Mixture of hydroxy compounds by I. R. and G. L. C.
B ₈₁ -B ₈₅	Petroleum ether : Benzene (1:1)	Nil	
B ₈₆ -B ₁₀₅	Benzene	White solid m.p. 102-103°C. 40 mg.	G. L. C. indicates one component containing 30 carbon atoms. I. R. shows the presence of -OH and =C=O group.
B ₁₀₆ -B ₁₁₅	Benzene : Ether (1:1)	Nil	
B ₁₁₆ -B ₁₂₀	Ether	Nil	

* Each fraction contains 10 ml. of eluent.

TABLE III

Fractions*	Eluents	Wt. of the material	T.L.C. Report.
C ₁	Benzene : Petroleum Ether : Chloroform (1:1:3)	5 mg.	One component
C ₂ -C ₃	-do-	13 mg.	Two components in equal amount.
C ₄	-do-	10 mg.	Two components, one in trace amount.
C ₅ -C ₈	-do-	90 mg.	One component.
C ₉ -C ₁₁	-do-	5 mg.	Two components, one in trace amount.
C ₁₂ -C ₁₇	-do-	10 mg.	One component.
C ₁₈ -C ₂₀	Benzene : Petroleum Ether : Chloroform (1:1:5)	Nil.	
C ₂₁ -C ₂₃	Benzene : Petroleum Ether : Chloroform (1:1:1)	Nil	

*Each fraction contains 10 ml. of eluent.

from these fractions after crystallization from petroleum ether (40°-60°) and benzene yielded a crystalline solid (I) m.p. 102°. $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 9^\circ (\text{CHCl}_3)$, $M^+ 452$, molecular formula $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{60}\text{O}_2$, does not give any colouration with tetranitromethane nor does it give any test for sterols and triterpenes. I.R. spectra shows absorption at 3210 cm^{-1} (—O—H stretching due to polymeric association), 1700 cm^{-1} (=C=O carbonyl), 1455 cm^{-1} (—CH₂ bending), 1375 cm^{-1} (—C—CH₂ bending), 1066 cm^{-1} (—C—O stretching of secondary alcohol), doublet 727 and 718 cm^{-1} (—(CH₂)_n bending ($n > 4$) vibration due to straight chain methylene groups. These data clearly indicate that (I) is a hydroxy ketone.

The absolute identification of higher aliphatic ketone has given great trouble on account of very similar physical properties, and I.R. and N.M.R. spectra. The fragmentations obtained in mass spectra have been of immense help in elucidating the structure of higher aliphatic ketones, both symmetrical and unsymmetrical⁶⁻⁸. The most intense peaks are obtained by α fission and also by β fission which is accompanied by McLafferty rearrangement with the addition of plus one ion. The structure of the ketone (I) was determined from MS study. In the MS of the ketone (I) no significant M-15 was observed and the ratio of (M-15)⁺/M⁺ was close to zero. This

indicates that the ketone has a straight chain⁹. MS showed M+1 peak characteristic of unsymmetrical ketones¹⁰.

In the mass spectrum m/e 185 (33 percent, α fission to the carbonyl group), m/e 295 (66 percent, α fission to the carbonyl group), m/e 200 (100 percent, β -fission, McLafferty plus one ion), m/e 213 (9 percent, γ fission to the carbonyl group), m/e 227 (7 per cent, δ fission), m/e 310 (100 percent β fission, McLafferty plus one ion), m/e 323 (9 percent, γ fission to the carbonyl group), m/e 337 (5 per cent, δ fission), m/e 29 (23 percent, α fission to the hydroxyl group), m/e 59 (44 percent, α fission to the hydroxyl group). All these characteristic peaks can be well accounted for with the structure I.

Treatment of the fractions of Table III

Fractions C₅-C₁₀ were found to be a single component by T.L.C. However G.L.C. (Fig. 1 and 2) revealed that it was a mixture of 5 components with carbon content ranging from C₂₇-C₃₁, odd number of carbon atoms prevailing, only minute traces of

compounds with even number were present. One of the compounds is identical with hentriacontan-16-ol¹¹ which was prepared synthetically from palmitone¹² by sodium borohydride reduction.

Treatment of the chloroform extract

The residue from the chloroform extract which had a fishy odour on being heated with dilute alkali gave profuse quantity of methylamine. From the neutral moiety of this fraction β -sitosterol was obtained after chromatographic separation over alumina. A waxy solid was eluted with petroleum ether which showed carbonyl absorption in the IR at 1740 cm^{-1} (KBr disc) indicating the presence of ester in it. T.L.C. showed two spots—one very weak. The major spot had R_f 0.60 (5% ether to petroleum ether) corresponding to esters of high molecular weight. The ketone m.p. $85^\circ\text{--}86^\circ$ isolated from this fraction by Chatterji *et al.*⁵ could not be traced.

Treatment of the ethanolic extract

The residue obtained from the ethanolic extract which contained the saponin was hydrolysed with alcoholic hydrogen chloride when a crude genin was obtained which on chromatographic separation over alumina yielded a pure genin m.p. $304^\circ\text{--}305^\circ$ [$\alpha_D^{25} + 175$ [EtOH.]] The work on the saponin is in progress and will be shortly published.

Experimental

Powdered leaves (320 g) of *Marsilea minuta* Linn was extracted successively with petroleum ether (b.p. $60^\circ\text{--}80^\circ$), chloroform and ethanol.

Treatment of Petroleum Ether extract

The petroleum ether extract on removal of the solvent yielded a dark green solid. The solid was dried and the dried residue (5 g), was chromatographed on a column of neutral Brockmann alumina (200 g), as in Table I. Fractions $A_{46}\text{--}A_{110}$ from this chromatography were rechromatographed over Argentized silica gel (10 g) as in Table II. Only one pure component was separated during this chromatography in benzene elution and this on crystallisation from Petroleum ether-benzene mixture yielded a plate shaped crystal (30 mg.), m.p. 102° . $M^+(452)$, [$\alpha_D^{25} - 9^\circ$ (CHCl_3)] (Found C, 79.70 ; H, 13.01%. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{60}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 79.64 ; H, 13.27%).

Again the fractions ($B_{21}\text{--}B_{80}$) obtained during this chromatography was rechromatographed third time on Argentized silica gel (Table III) and each fraction of this chromatography product was carefully examined. Major fractions ($C_5\text{--}C_8$) of this chromatography appeared to be one component by T.L.C. and I.R. showed it to be a straight chain compound containing hydroxyl group. But by the study of G.L.C. (Fig. 1 and 2) it was found to be the mixture

Fig. 1. Bold line—Mixture of hydroxy compounds from $C_5\text{--}C_8$ fractions. Dotted line—Hydroxy Ketone (I) from $B_{86}\text{--}B_{106}$ fractions.

Fig. 2. Circle—Standard compounds, Circle with a dot at the centre—hydroxy Ketone (I), triangles—Mixture of hydroxy compounds from B_{88} — B_{105} fractions, square—Synthetic 16—hydroxy-hentriacontane.

of five components containing carbon atoms from C_{27} — C_{31} . One of the components was found to be 16-hydroxyhentriacontane, compared with an authentic sample prepared from Palmitone by its reduction with sodium borohydride.

Treatment of Chloroform extract

After removing the solvent the residue (30 g) was heated on a water bath with 5% NaOH solution. The issuing gas was absorbed in 2(N) hydrochloric acid. The acid was completely removed under reduced pressure and then the residue was crystallized from water when the hydrochloride crystallizes as needles, m.p. 224° . (Found N, 20.62% ; CH_6NCl requires 20.74%).

2:4-dinitromethyl aniline derivative (m.p. 174 — 75° , literature 175°) was prepared by passing the issuing gas through a cold ethanolic solution of 2:4-dinitrochlorobenzene (Found N, 21.45% ; $C_7N_3H_7O_4$ requires 21.32%).

The residue was filtered and washed with water to remove alkali as far as possible. It was dissolved in chloroform, washed with water till it was free of alkali. Chloroform was removed by distillation and the residue was chromatographed on a column of neutral Brockmann alumina eluting successively with petroleum ether (40° — 60°), benzene, chloroform and methanol used successively in a gradient elution procedure. Petroleum ether eluents give a mixture of hydrocarbon and ester and benzene eluent gives β -sitosterol as some major components.

Identification of β -sitosterol

The product obtained in the benzene eluent crystallized from chloroform : methanol (1:1) as colourless flakes m.p. 135° — 136° . $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ -35 (in chloroform). This was fairly soluble in benzene, methanol and ethanol and readily soluble in chloroform, ether and ethyl acetate. It was identified as β -sitosterol and found not to depress the m.p. of an authentic sample of β -sitosterol (Found : C, 83.80 ; H, 12.01% ; $C_{29}H_{50}O$ requires C, 84.05 ; H, 12.08%). ν_{max} 3400 cm^{-1} (OH) ; Acetate (pyridine—acetic anhydride mixture), crystallized from chloroform : methanol (1:1), m.p. 125° — 126° (reported 126°) ; Benzoate (pyridine-benzoyl chloride), m.p. 142° — 143° (reported 144°).

Treatment of Ethanolic extract

Ethanol was removed from the ethanolic extract and the crude saponin, as dark brown hygroscopic powder (40 g) was hydrolysed with 6% ethanolic hydrochloric acid (250 ml.) at reflux for 24 hours. Alcohol was evaporated off on water bath keeping the volume same on frequent addition of water. It was then filtered and the residue was dried and the dried residue 20 g. was chromatographed on a column of neutral Brockmann alumina (400 g) elution being carried out successively with petroleum ether (40° — 60°), benzene, chloroform and methanol in a gradient elution procedure. Fraction eluted with chloroform methanol mixture (19:1) gives slight brown coloured solid which on crystallisation from ethanol gives needle shaped crystals, m.p. 304° — 5° [α] 25 +175 [EtOH].

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